

pregledi - mi slewa - di lemi

**INFORMI RAWETO NA SLEPI TE -
ME\U REALNOTO I MO@NOTO ^I -
TAM, SLU[AMI PI [UVAM-ZNA^I POSTOJAM**

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Rezi me

Javnost informirane, praktično, postoji otkoga i neovako kako općenito bitno; no njegove metode i sredstva postojano se unapređivani suglasno razvojne tekove na općenite odnose i tehničko-tehnološki razvoj.

Suvremene demokratske odredbe na sekciji civilizirano općenito je proklamirano i omogućava slobodan javnost informirane kako su testvena determinanta neovakovo opstojavaju.

Danas pravost na informirane i jedno od osnovne neovakove prava deklarirano u brojne međunarodne dokumente, u ustavnim na glavni broj zemlje u svetost koju i u ustavot na Republika Makedonija.

Informirane na slepi te li ca so celokupni ot kompleks na specifičnosti ne emone da se razvija nadvor od sistemot i tekove na javnost informirane u potpuno irokata zajednica. Pri toa treba da se ima predvid deka informirane na slepite li ca bar identične, no i svoevremeni tretman kako poprati svojata ekskluzivnost, tako i sporedne prednosti i tehničke u socijalni ot kontekst na sekvencijata komunikacija.

Toa sekako ne može da bude nadvor od neodgovorno finansiranje na informirane ta dejnost na slepi te li ca, osobeno na segmentni ov stepen na razvoj na informacione sisteme i unapređivane neovakove i te prava.

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views - opinions - dilemmas

**INFORMING BLIND PEOPLE –
BETWEEN REALITY AND POSSIBILITY
I READ, HEAR AND WRITE – I EXIST**

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Abstract

Public information, actually, has existed since people became social beings; but its methods and means have always been improved in regard to the developing processes of social relations and technical and technological development.

Contemporary democratic commitments of any civilized society proclaim and enable the freedom of public information as an essential determinant of human existence. Today the right to information is one of the basic human rights declared in many international documents, in the constitutions of a great number of countries in the world, as well as in the Constitution of the Republic of Macedonia. Informing blind people about the complex of specifics is not possible to develop out of the system and the processes of public information in the wider community. It has to be taken into consideration that information to blind requires identical and appropriate treatment because of its exclusiveness and priorities and techniques in the social context of entire communication. That can not be out of the appropriate financing of information activities of blind, especially at this level of development of information systems and development of human rights.

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Klu-ni zborovi: javno inf ormi rawe, sle-pi li ca, ~ovekovi prava na inf ormi rawe, posebni inf ormacijski sist emi

*Koji ma o~i neka gleda,
neka `i vee so o~it e,
o~it e se golema radost !
Gladni t e o~i
bi go izele cel iot svet !
^uvajt e gi o~it e!
Ne gi davajt e o~it e!*

Du{ an Radovi }
"Crn den#

I navisti na ako ~ovekot na krajot od svo-jot beskrajno dol grazvoj do{ ol do stavot: "Dodeka ne vidam, nema da veruvam#, ako toj stav pretstavuva kul mi nacija na ~ovekovata mudrost i najgolemo dostignuvawe na negoviot razum, toga{ svetot na sløpi-te e navisti na beden, plitok i, { to e naj-va`no, nenerlivo zdodeven svet.

Javnoto inf ormi rawe, prakti ~no, postoi otkoga e i ~ovekot kako op{ testveno bi-tie; no negovite metodi i sredstva postojano se unapreduvani. Sekoga{ , sl ødej} i gi razvojni te tekovi na op{ testvenite od-nosi i tehnolog i te, toa denes dosti gnal o ne samo neo~ekuvano ni vo, tuku i vl ijani e. Kako retko kade i so osoben interes vo nego se vgradeni vrvni dostignuvawa od naukata i tehnikata, taka { to na negoviot razvoen pat re~isi nema ve}e ni kakvi ob-jektivni bari eri i ograni ~uvawa.

Sovremeni te, razvi eni te i demokratski te opredel bi na edno op{ testvo ja prokl ami -raat i ja ovozm o` uvaat sl obodata na javno-to inf ormi rawe i za toa sozdavaat neop-hodni pretpostavki i uslovi. Toa pridone-slo da se sozdade cel osen sistem { to vo sebe gi vkl u-va si te tri bi tni segmenti na inf ormi raweto-izvori te, tekovi te i korisni cite, { to mu dava osobena kohe-zi ona mo}, verodostojnost i vpe~atlivost.

Key words: public information, blind people, human rights to information, special informa-tion systems.

*Let one who has eyes see,
Let one live with the eyes,
Eyes are a great joy!
Hungry eyes
would eat the whole world!
Take care of the eyes!
Do not give up the eyes!*

Dushan Radovikj
"Black Day"

People throughout their endless development could consider "Unless I see it, I do not be-lieve it", and if this attitude is a culmination of people's wisdom and the greatest achievement of their reason, the world of blind is really miserable, shallow and the most important – an immeasurably boring world.

Public information, practically, has existed since people became social beings; and its methods and means have always been im-proved. Following up the developing courses in social relations and technologies, it has reached not only an unexpected level but influence, as well. Outstanding achievements in science and technology are built up in information as no-where else and with special interest, so there are almost no objective barriers and limitations on its path of development.

Contemporary, developed and democratic commitments of a society proclaim and enable the freedom of public information and make necessary assumptions and conditions. That has contributed to a creation of a complete system that includes the three essential segments of in-formation – sources, courses and users, which give it a special cohesive power, truth, impres-sion.

Toa prakti~no stana op{ tonarodno dobro, postojano prisutno i dostapno za site so neograni~eni mo`nosti na selekcija, procenka i poinawe.

Otvoren e { irok prostor za site sprema svoje mo`nosti, sposobnosti i afinite ti da u~estvuvaat vo procesite na toj sistem i taka da ostvaruvaat { irok spektar na dejstvuvawe i vlijanie, i da si gi obezbeduvaat op{ tite i psoebnite interesi i potrebi vo ova oblast.

Pravoto na informirawe e edno od osnovnite ~ovekovi prava deklarirano vo site me|unarodni dokumenti, no i vo ustavite na najgolemi ot broj zemji na svetot, me|ukoi i vo na{ i ot ustav.

No vo Makedonija Zakonot za pristap do informacii u{ te e vo faza na podgotovka. Spored **rezultati te od istra`uvaweto na javnoto mislewe, sprovedeno od gra|anskata organizacija "Transparentnost Makedonija"** za pristap do informacii te, duri 41% od ispitani te gra|ani u{ te ne znaat deka ni vnoto pravo do informacii te e **zagarrantirano so Ustavot**, odnsno deka imaat zagarrantirano pravo na pristap do informacii, odnosno deka bezmal ku sekoj vtor ~ovek vo Makedonija ne znae deka ima pravo na takov pristap. Od druga strana, porazitel en e brojot na gra|ani koi ne pobarale informacii od dr`avnata admnistracija, a se o~ekuva ni vni ot broj, navisti na, da bi de pogolem. Najmnogu e porazitel en podatokot deka 74% od ispitani cite koi ne dobi le informacii, ne napravile ni { to ponatamu. Re~isi nema vlast na zemjite vo tranzicija { to e gotovna vedna{ i vo sekoe vreme da gi done se zakoni te { to }e i ja naru{ at komocijata vo vladeweto.

Toga{ , ako vo zemja, kako na{ ava, vo koja nedostiga organiziran sistem za komunikacija so gra|anite, nema lice { to kako pretstavnik na institucii te, na primer na ministerstvata, bi im gi davale baranite informacii na gra|anite, ako ima neefikasno vodewe evidencija za informacii te, odnosno nema mehанизam za davawe i sublimirawe na potrebnata informacija, ako ima samocenzura na vraboteni-

Information has become common social good, always present and accessible to everybody with unlimited possibilities for selection, evaluation and understanding.

Large space has been opened for people according to their possibilities, abilities and affinities to participate in the processes of that system, to implement a wide range of activities and inputs and to provide common and special interest and needs.

The right to information is one of the basic human rights declared in all international documents, in the constitutions of many countries in the world, as well as in our Constitution.

In the Republic of Macedonia, the law of access to information is still in preparatory phase. **According to the results of a research on public opinion, carried out by the NGO "Transparency Macedonia"** for an access to information, 41% of the interviewed people do not know that their right to information **is guaranteed by the Constitution**, i.e. almost every second person in Macedonia. On the other hand, the number of people who have not asked for any information from the state administration is enormous and it is even expected to enhance. The fact, 74% of those interviewed people who have not received any information, have not done anything further. There is almost no government in the countries of transition, which is ready immediately or at any time to pass laws and to disturb the commodity of governing.

In our country, without an organized system of communication with the public; without any real representatives of institutions (relevant ministries) to provide public with necessary information; without efficient registering of information, i.e. without a mechanism for giving or sublimating necessary information; employees in institutions provide public with censored

te vo institucii te i na gra|ani te im gi davaat samo oni e informacii { to mora da im gi dadat i ako na sevo ova se dodadat naviki te da se funkci oni ra preku vrski, toga{ se pra{ uvame: mo` e li i slep te gra|ani da imaat kakov-takov pristap do informacii, gotovni vo soodvetni tehnik i za niv. Sekako deka ne; i ako i tie, kako i drugi te gra|ani, navisti na se zainteresirani da se regulira pristapot do informacii te-sloboden, no reguliran so zakon.

Predlogzakonot za pristap do informacii te e ocenet kako soliden zakonski tekst, koj treba da se doraboti i kako takov bi bil prifatliv. **Potrebno e da se definira: { to se e pristap do informacii, koj ima pristap do niv, koi se isklucite, { to e tajna proglasena so zakon, niz koi proceduri mora da mine baraweto, koj treba da odgovori, koja e odgovornosta na institucijata i koja institucija } e go sproveduva zakonot.**

Od druga strana, kako edno od ustavnite prava i dol`nosti na gra|anite, javnoto informirawe e dejnost od posebno op{ testveno znaewe. **Vo otsustvo na vr{ewe na ova dejnost od dr`avata, Sojuzot na slep te na Republika Makedonija e primiden sam da gi utvrdi potrebite vo ova oblast i, vo soglasnost so mo`nosti te i uslovi te, da go ustanovuva unapreduva i pomaga razvojot na informativniot sistem na slep te, da obezbeduva popovolni materijalni, kadrovski i drugi mo`nosti.**

i vo taa smisla da gi pottiknuva nadle`nite op{ testveni faktori soodvetno da u-estvuvaat vo ova specifi~na dejnost koja-so sevkupni ot razvoj, organi zirawe i sodr`ina-treba da gi sledi promenite vo op{ testvoto i polo`bata na slepiot ~ovek kako gra|anin.

Jasno im e na si te deka ~ovekot znae onolku kolku { to e informiran. Toa mu e jasno i na slepiot ~ovek. A dali im e jasno na drugi te za toa kol kava e negovata "ed i glad za informacii #?

information, everything functions through nepotism. We ask ourselves whether blind people can have any access to information, prepared in appropriate techniques for them. Certainly not, although they, as other people, are interested really in regulated access to information – free but regulated by law.

The **draft law** of access to information has been considered as a good law text, which has to be worked out and accepted. **It has to be defined: what is access to information, who has access to information, what are the exceptions, what is secret proclaimed by law, through which procedures must the requirements pass, who has to reply to them, what is the institution's responsibility, which institution will implement the law?**

On the other hand, as one of the constitutional rights and obligations of people, the public information is an activity of common social importance. **In absence of state authorized provider of this activity, the Association of blind of the Republic of Macedonia, has to set up the needs in this filed, in accordance with its possibilities and conditions, to establish, improve and assist the development of the information system of blind, to provide friendlier material, personnel and other possibilities.**

It has to stimulate the authorized social factors to participate accordingly in this specific activity, which in the whole development, organization and content, **has to follow up the changes in the society and the position of blind as citizens.**

It is clear to everyone that one knows as much as one is informed. This is also clear to blind people. Is it clear to others how big is one's "thirst and hunger for information"?

Informirawet o na slepi te kako segment na informaciski te sist emi na op{ t est vot o

Informiraweto na slepi te li ca ne mo` e da nastane i da se razvi va nadvor od sistemot i tekovite na sistemot za javnoto informirawe vo po{ irokata zaednica. Vo taa smisla, toa e del od sistemot i vo sé bara i denti~en tretman poradi svojata ekskluzivnost i poradi soodvetni te prioriteti.

Toa, vo prv red, se odnesuva i na f i n a n s i raweto na informativnata dejnost za slepi te, koja dosega voop{ to ne e uredena vo zakonski te propisi, pred sé, so Zakonot za javno informirawe. Do pred dve godini soodvetni sredstva za ova a namena se dobi vaa od Mini sterstvoto za kul tura, { to ni pribli` no ne bea dovolni, ta vo gol em del spi sanijata se al i menti raat od avtohtoni te sredstva na Sojuzot i li preku projekti.

Sozdadeni se tehni~ki i drugi pretpostavki za nepre~ena podgotovka, produkcija i distribucija na informativni te glasila za slepite so Brajovoto pismo i so zvu~na tehni ka. Sosema e sé edno dali i n f o r m a t i v n a t a d e j n o s t n a s l e p i t e } e b i d e d e l o d d e j n o s t a n a S o j u z o t n a s l e p i t e i l i } e b i d e v o r a m k i t e n a i z d a v a - k o - i n f o r m a t i v n i o t c e n t a r, o s n o v a n v o r a m k i t e n a F r a n c u s k o - m a k e d o n s k i o t m a k r o p r o e k t " F a r e - B r a j # , { t o v o S o j u z o t n a s l e p i t e n a R M s e s p r o v e d e o d 2 0 0 0 d o 2 0 0 2 g o d i n a k a k o z a s e b n a i n s t i t u c i j a s o s t a t u s n a s a m o s t o j n a u s t a n o v a . P r i t o a , s e k a k o , b i t n o e d a s e p o s t i g n e c e l o s n a i n f o r m i r a n o s t n a s l e p i t e l i c a , z a o p { t i t e i p o s e b n i t e p r a { a w a n a s l e p i t e i t o a d a s e o s t v a r i v o s o g l a s n o s t s o s o o d v e t n i t e s t a n d a r d i i n a v i s o k o k v a l i t a t i v n o n i v o .

Vo sekoj slu~aj sredstvata za informirawe za slepi te mora da bidat vo centarot na vnimani eto na Sojuzot na slepi te i predmet na negovo osobeno vnimani e i gri` a, za da dojde do celosen izraz ni vnata didakti~ka i informativna uloga, kako i da bidat vo celost realizirani ni vni te zada~i;

Information of blind as a segment of information systems in the society

Information of blind cannot exist and develop out of the system and courses of the system for public information of the community. In this sense, it is a part of the system and it requires in everything an identical treatment **because of its exclusiveness and appropriate priorities.**

That, firstly, refers to financing of the information activities for blind, which has not been regulated by law so far, i.e. by the Law of Public Information. The Ministry of Culture provided funds allocated for this purpose until 2 years ago, which were not sufficient, and a large number of magazines were alimented by the autochthonous funds of the Association through projects.

Technical and other assumptions have been created for undisturbed preparation, production and distribution of informative media for blind with Braille alphabet and sound technique. It is not essential whether the information activity of blind will be a part of the activities of the Association of Blind or within **the publishing and information center, founded by French-Macedonian Macro Project "Phare-Braille"**, implemented by the Association of Blind of the Republic of Macedonia from 2000 to 2002 with the status of independent institution. It is very important to provide information to blind on common and special issues of blind and to implement it according to appropriate standards and high quality level.

In any case, information means for blind must be attention-centered of the Association of Blind in order to provide didactic and information role of it, as well as to implement all their tasks;

{ to poefikasno da se supstituiraa za slepите nedostapnite medijima i da se obezbedat { to poadekvatni uslovi za celosno informirawe vo soodvetnit ehnik, dostapni za niv.

Pokraj toa, treba re{itelno da se nastojuva { to pobrgu da se osvojat i primenat novite tehnikidostignuvawa vo elektronskata tehnologija, ekskluzivni ili kompatibilni so patitata i metode na informirawe za slepите.

Specifičnost i na informativnata dejnost za slepите i bitnite pretpostavki za realizirawe

Informativnata dejnost, spored prirodanarabotite, e edna od prioritetnizadavivorabotata na organizacijite na slepите.

Informativnata dejnost na Sojuzot na slepите na Makedonija, vo soglasnost so celnata grupa na korisnici, mo`e da se podeli na vnatre{na, t.e. interna, i navore{na, odnosno eksterna; a vo soglasnost so tehnikite vo koi se proizveduvana Brajova i navu~na. I zstanuva crni otpe~at i primenata na elektronskata (digitalna) tehnika. Sepak, krucijalno mesto vo informiraweto na slepите im pripa|a na Brajovite i vuni te spisanija { to gi izdava Sojuzot na slepите na Makedonija. Toa se tipinigliasila so konvencionalni karakteristiki, specijalni samo po tehnikata i namenata, specifi~ni po prezentiranata ekskluzivna problematika.

Ona { to gi pravi nenadomestlivi i mnoguzna~ajni vo sferata na informiraweto na slepите, toa e bogatstvoto na nivnata tematika, razli~niot pristap i vid na novinarski izraz, struna ili popularna obrabotka, originalnost i aktuelnost. Brajoviot pe~ate po`eleni osobeno korisen, amago nema dovolno, kako { to i brojot na ~itatelite { to go koristi e proporcionalnomal (okolu 300 ~iteli) vo odnos na brojnosta na drugite kategorii ~iteli.

to substitute unreachable media for blind and to provide equal conditions for information with appropriate and available techniques.

Besides that, there is a need of decisive attempt for faster implementation of new technical achievements in electronic technology, exclusive or compatible to ways and methods of information of blind.

Specifics of information activity for blind and essential assumptions for its implementation

Information activity, according to its nature, is one of the priority tasks of Organizations of Blind.

Information activity of the Association of Blind of the Republic of Macedonia, according to the target group of users, can be divided in internal and external; and according to the techniques to Braille and sound. Black print and application of electronic (digital) technology is missing. Still, the crucial position in information of blind belongs to Braille and sound magazines issued by the Association of Blind of the Republic of Macedonia.

They are specific media with conventional characteristics, with special technique and purposes and specific for presented exclusive problems.

The richness of their themes, different approach and kind of journalistic expression, professional and popular processing, ingenuity and current event make them indispensable and very important in the sphere of information of blind

The Braille print is desirable and useful, but it is very scarce. The number of readers who use it is proportionally small (about 300 readers) in relation to the number of other categories of readers.

Kasetnata tehnika i natamu solidno go odrabotuva svojot del i koleblivo ~ekori me|u dve ograni ~enosti. I ako e najmasovna vo opslu` uvaweto na slepите li ca, taa ve}e e nadmi nata i, prakti ~no, odumi ra; dodeka nejzi nata nezamenli va suverenost na na{ i te prostori pretstavuvaat posl edni te usil bi so koi se og lasu va vo E`vropa. Koga stanuva zbor za zvu~nata tehnika, idni nata, bez somnenie, mu pripa|a na kompakt-di skot.

Elektronskata, odnosno di gi tal nata f orma na spi sani jata vo organi zaci i te na slepите vo Makedonija, za `al, a i kako sig nal za vi sti nska uzbuna, za pove}eto u{ te e vi sti nska nepoznata, a za sosema retki te i "povl asteni te# e vlez vo i dni nata.

Sé pove}e i ma spi sani ja { to vo Evropa se sni maat na CD-a, a del od ni v mo` e da gi preslu{ ate i preku i nternet, ili od mre` ata da gi vmetnete vo kompjuterot.

Uloga na medi uni t e

Vo Francija i vo Angli ja nadvladuva i nteresot za usovr{ uvawe na dostrel ot na i nformati ~kata tehnol ogi ja. Kaj ni v e vo tek izrabotka i ostvaruvawe raznovi dni proekti. Vo vrska so pre~ki te vo pri sta pot do i nformaci i te i kul turata Stiven King od Kralski ot naci onal en i nsti tut za slepите vo Vel i ka Bri tani ja go navedu va pri merot na pri stapot na bi bli oteki te preku telef on. Vrz toj principi r`o bat bibliotekite vo Erusalim i Tel Aviv. Toa e slo`ena stru~na tema koja najednostavno mo` e da se svede na sled noto: ~itatelite so ovie biblioteki se povrzani vo mre` a i so ni v mo` e da komu niciraat preku telef onskata linija. Na toj na~in tie imaat direkten uvid vo sodr` i nata na f ondovi te i mo` e potreb nata kniga da ja prezemat na hard disk, mo` e da ja i skopi raat na soodveten elek tronski nositel na i nformaci i i trajno da ja zadr` at vo li ~nata bi bli oteka, ili da ja izbri { at ako za ni v nema trajna vrednost.

The cassette technique still solidly works out its part and uncertainly ranges between two limitations. Although it is the most mass-technique that serves the blind people, it is out of date and practically dies out while its indispensable sovereignty, in our region, is the last attempt to harmonize with Europe. Without no doubt, when sound technique is in question, the future lies in compact discs.

The electronic, i.e. digital form of magazines in the organizations for blind in Macedonia, unfortunately and as a signal for real alarm is still real unknown value for a great number of people and for a very small number of "privileged" people means access to future.

There are a great number of magazines in Europe that are recorded on CDs and a part of them one can listen to on the Internet or to download them from web sites.

The role of media

The interest for improving the range of information technique prevails in France and England. Various projects are under production there. In relation to the obstacles for approaching the information and culture, Stephen King from Royal National Institute for Blind in Great Britain quotes the example of approach to libraries through phone. The libraries in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv utilize this principle. It is a complex professional topic, which can simply be described that the readers are connected through nets to libraries and they can communicate with them through telephone lines. Thus, they have direct insight in the content of funds and can download the required book on hard disc. They can copy it on appropriate electronic information carrier and keep it in their library forever or erase it if the book does not have permanent value in their opinion.

Slepoto lice }e ja koristi so pomo{ na zvu~ni ot izlez ili so Brajov di splej, a po potreba mo`e da ja ope~ati na Brajovo ili standardno pismo, odnosno da ja iskopi ra na disketa. Sevo ova mo`e da se sra boti so pomo{ na mal kompjuterski sistem, no pod uslov da im e dostapen na mn ozi na slepi li ca.

Takvi ot na~in na komuni kacija od osnova gi menuva tradicionalnite oblici za rabota i na bibliotekarstvoto voop{ to. Nema ve}e potreba za voobi~aena distri bucija preku po{ ta; nema duri ni potreba za tradi conal nata pe~atena ili zvu~na kni ga, na kakva { to sme navi knal e. Za nas toa u{ te e mnogu daleku, no so brzi ili so bavni ~ekori progresot eden den sigurno }e stasa i do nas. Pretpostavki te za ostvaruvawe na ovie inovaci i podraz biraat visoko ni vo na tehni ~ka opreme nost i na biblioteki te i na ni vni te ko risni ci, a isto taka i soodvetno stru~no znaewe, bez { to site sovre meni uredi ostanuvaat nadvor od upotreba.

Od druga strana, internet-spi sani jata se javuvaat vo tekstualen oblik. Stanuva zbor za elektronski magazini { to poodel ni izdava~i gi ispra}aat kako pri vrzok vo elektronskata poraka, taka { to za samo nekol ku mi nuti na kompjuterot go imate novi ot broj na spi sani eto. Ni vnata uredenost i preglednost e na visoko ni vo, bi dej}i lesno i brgu mo`e da go otvori te posakuvani ot pril og, podgotven vo soodveten edi tor na tekst.

I na Zapad se retki cel osni izdani ja na soodveten dneven vesnik vo bi lo koja tehni ka za slepite li ca, ta naj~esto se pri begnuvalo kon selektivno ~itawe, preku radi oto ili telef onot, a vo ponovo vreme i vo elektronska forma, odnosno so pomo{ na kompjuterot.

Kompjuterskata tehnologija ovozm o`uva slepi ot ~ovek da ima pred sebe mo`nost za cel osna inf ormi ranost, bi dej}i orga nizaci i te na slepi te se obi del e ovoj problem da go re{ at preku Brajovi ili zvu~ni publikaci i. Sepak, kolku da se tie uspe{ ni, ostanuva prazni nata vo inf ormi ranosta na slepi te li ca.

The blind person will use the book assisted by sound output or Braille display and, if needed, they can print it in Braille or standard letters, i.e. copy on diskette. This can be done with a small computer system if it is available to the majority of blind people.

Such way of communication essentially changes the traditional forms for work and the library activity in general. There is no need of usual distribution by mail; there is no need for traditional printed or sound book we used to know. It is still far away for us, but the progress will reach us with fast or slow steps, for sure. The assumptions for implementation of these innovations require high level of technical equipment of both, libraries and their users, as well as appropriate professional knowledge that is required for utilization of all modern devices.

On the other hand, the Internet magazines appear in text forms. It is a case with certain publishers, that send attachments in E-mails and in a few minutes, one can have the new magazine issue in the computer. Their editing and arrangement are on high level because one can open easily and fast the desired item, prepared in appropriate text editor.

Complete issues of certain daily newspaper in any technique for blind are utterly rare in the west. Most frequently, a selective reading has been applied, through radio or telephone and nowadays in electronic form, i.e. with computers.

The computer technology allows the blind person to have the possibility for complete information. Thus, the organizations for blind tried to solve that problem successfully through Braille or sound publications. Nevertheless, there is a gap in information for the blind.

Slepi lo i problemi so internet

I ma mnogu ograni~uvawa postaveni pred slepite korisnici na internetot. I pri pra}aweto i pri prezewaweto na elektronskata po{ ta, isto taka postojat soodvetni te{ kotii, za ~ie odstranuwawe se bara re{ enie. Prebaruwaweto e soo~eno so mnogu te{ kotii, bidej}i internetot e celi ot vo sliki. Tekstot ne e najva`en; i koga go ima pristapot mu e mnogu slo`en, bidej}i te{ ko mo`e da se izdvoi od drugi vizuelni elementi. A spisanijata i publikaciite, prezentirani na internet, mnogu ~esto ne se dadeni za slepoto lice da mo`e vedna{ da gi upotrebi. Najgol ema pre~ka se vizuelni te ilustracii, bidej}i zvu~nite ~ita~i na ekranot ne se vo sostojba brgu da se pref rluvaat od ilustraciite na tekstot, taka { to vo toa pref rluwawe }e se spletkaat i pravat zastoj vo rabotata. Poradi toa formi rawe na eden virtuelen informativen centar bi bil vistinska mo`nost za spisanijata, publikaciite, knigite i sl. da se podgotvat i da se dovedat vo oblik za brzo i efikasno kori stewe na soodvetni ot sajt.

Virtuelni ot informativen centar bi mo`el da dade gol em pri dones vo zapoznavaweto so pol iti ~kata kul tura i za namal uwawe propustite vo inf ormi raweto. Toj ovozno` uva najvi soko ni vo na ramnopravnost me|u licata so vid i slepite lica. Licata so vid }e se soo~uvaat so di lemata: Taa ramnopravnost zasega uspealo da ja postigne edinstveno radi oto. Taka po~nuwawe so eden proben proekt bi bil prv ~ekor, vistinski poteg.

Za slepite korisnici na virtuelni ot informativen centar od golemo zna~ewe se razli~nite komentari, analizi, knigi, pri kazi, zanimlivosti, sportski pregl edi, radio i televizi ski te programi, trendovite vo modata; so eden zbor, s{ to gi interesira i lu|eto so vid. Vo Velika Britanija, Francija i SAD razli~ni organizacii na slepite i za slepite se zanimavaat so podgotovka na elektronski izdanija na razli~ni dnevni vesnici i peri odika.

Blindness and problems with the Internet

There are many limitations for blind users of the Internet. There are certain difficulties in receiving and sending electronic mail and a solution for their elimination is required. The searching is faced with many troubles because the Internet is full of pictures. The text cannot be considered the most important part and the approach to it is very complex because it can be hardly separated from other visual elements. The magazines and publications presented on the Internet are not often fit for blind person's immediate use. Visual illustrations are the greatest obstacle because screen sound readers are not able quickly to transfer from illustration to text and so they confuse and create delays in their performance. Establishment of a virtual information center would be real possibility the magazines, publications, books and others to be prepared and shaped for quick and efficient use of the appropriate site.

The virtual information center might greatly contribute to information on political culture and to the reduction of failures in information. It enables the highest level of equality between people with good vision and blind ones.

The radio only has achieved that equality. Thus, the first step, the real act will be the beginning a trial project.

Different comments, analysis, books, reviews, interesting items, sport reviews, radio and TV programs, fashion trends are of great importance for the blind users of virtual information center; i.e. the same that interest people with vision.

Various organizations for blind in Great Britain, France and USA deal with preparations for electronic issues of various daily newspapers and periodicals.

Podgotovkata se izvr{uva na toj na-in {to zainteresirani ot vesnik ja dostavuva elektronskata verzija, a stru~wacite vo organizacii te ja ureduvaat na toj na-in {to slepoto lice mo`e bez te{kotii da go koristi tekstualni ot del.

Pred pojavata na kompjuterskata tehnologija slepите ги користеле и u{te ги koristat radio i televiziските stanici za da dostignat soodvetno nivo na informiranost. No pi{anite informacii ne im se dostupni, a se zna~aen faktor za izvestuvawe vo op{tokulturnata oblast.

Internata informativna dejnst na Sojuzot po priroda na rabotite e svrtena isklu~itelno kon ~lenstvoto na Sojuzot na slepите i imaprvenstvena zada~a navreme i objektivno da go informira za nastanite vo zdru`enijata na slepите lica za aktuelnite problemi, sostojbata i aktuelnostite na site poliwa od rabotata i dejstvuvaweto na Sojuzot i organizacii te na slepите. Vo Makedonija kako edinstveni interni spisanija se pe~atat mese~nicite: **Brajovoto spisanie "Na{ Zbor#** i zvu~noto spisanie **"Panorama#**, kako oficijalni glasila na Sojuzot na slepите na Makedonija, {to popove}egodi {nata pauza po~naa kontunirano da se izdavaat od po~etokot na 1997 godina.

Od druga strana, eksterni ot pe~at, t.e. onoj koj se izleguva vo po{ i rokata javnost osobeno e ~uvstvitelno pra{awe na koe {to pobrgu treba da mu se posveti posebno vni manie bi dej}i stanuva zbor za mediumi {to imaat dopolnitelni obvrski i zada~i. Vo poslednive nekolku godini taafunkcija ja vr{i radioenisijata **"Pantarei#** {to sekoj ponedelnik, od 14 do 15 ~asot, se emituva na branovite na **Makedonskoto radio, Radio Skopje**, ~ij urednik i voditel e avtorot na ovoj trud. **Enisijata po~na da se emituva na 28 oktombri 2000 godina** I ma odvreme-navreme i drugi emisii {to treba da se poddr`at, zaedni~ki da se osmisluvaat i da se unapreduvaat i toa vo sorabotka so { i rok krug aktivisti.

The preparation is carried out in a way that the newspaper delivers its electronic version and the professionals from the organizations edit it in a way that the blind can be able to use the text part without any difficulty.

Before the computer technique was born, the blind had used and still use radio and TV stations for information. However, written information is out of their reach, although they are a significant part for information on common culture.

The internal information activity of the Association is directed, naturally, towards the Association of blind members and its task is prompt and objective information for the events that happen in the associations for blind, current problems, situation and current events of the Association activities and the organizations for blind. Here in Macedonia, the only internal newspapers are the **Braille magazine "Nash zbor (Our Word)"** and the sound magazine **"Panorama"** as official gazettes of the Association for blind of Macedonia, which, after a long break, started again at the beginning of 1997.

The external press, i.e. the one for broader public, is especially a sensible issue, which, as soon as possible, should be paid special attention because such media have additional obligations and tasks. In the recent years, this function has been performed with the **radio program "Pantarei"** which is broadcasted on **Macedonian Radio, Radio Skopje** from 14:00 to 15:00 o'clock on Mondays. The editor and the host of that radio program is the author of this paper. **This radio program started its broadcast on 28 October 2000.** From time to time, there are other programs, which have to be supported, created and improved in cooperation with many activists.

Radi oemi si i te se visti nski most odnosno ubav na~in da se premosti jazot me|u slep i te i licata so vid; toa e i real na mo`nost za uspe{ na integracija vo op{ testvenata sredina, t.e. vo vidnoto opkru`uvawe. Preku ni v i mame otvoren premi n do si te segmenti na op{ testvenata zaedni ca, pa i do soodvetni te slu`bi { to re{avaat se do pra{ awata od interes za popul acijata so o{ teten vi d.

Sovremeni te streme` i na dene{ ni ot razvoj odat kon zadovoluvawe na si te specifi ~ni potrebi za ramnopraven razvoj i na slep i te li ca, taka { to osnovaweto na virtuel ni ot i nformati ven centar, si ste mi te za potrebi te na slep i te li ca, bi bi l ~ekor napred vo ovozmo`uvawe ramnopravno u~estvo na sl ep i te li ca vo op{ testveni ot razvoj.

Kako, koga i kade }e se urbanizira informaciski ot sist emza slep i te

Vo zemjava se pe~atat pove}e i ljadi regi stri rani spisanija od dnevni do godi { ni. Kako vo toa more da se snajdete i na slep i te da im go ovozmo` i te so ustav zagarantiranoto pravo za informirawe na gra|anite, kako i za sloboda na javni ot zbor?

Ne mora da se vpu{ tame vo detal i za teo ri jata na komuni kacijata, ni da ras~lenuvame za kodni ot kanal, kodni ot { um i sl. kako da se spravat so i zobi lstvoto i nformacii, bi dej}i kolku i da ni se nam dragi i potrebni, i kolku i da gi konsumi rame, ne samo { to ne }e mo` e i fizi ~ki (bi o{ ki) si te da gi primi me i zapomni me, tuku tokmu toa izobilstvo }e ja iskri vi na{ ata sli ka za nastani te i nepovol no }e vli jae vrz ~ekori te { to }e gi prezememe. Nasproti ni v, se pogolem e brojot na slep i te { to se osameni, i li i toa kako ` el ni za, visti nski za ni v, pri jatno dru{ tvo, duri i koga se so potesnoto semejstvo. Za toa za ni v e visti nski mal prazni k koga po{ tarot }e im zayvoni na vratata. Ne zaradi toa { to toj e ni vnoto visti nsko dru{ tvo, po koe kopneat (i ako bi mo` el

The radio programs are a real bridge, i.e. fine way to overcome the gap between the blind and people with vision; it is a real possibility for successful integration in social environment, i.e. visual environment. The radio programs provide open pass to all segments of social community and relevant services, as well as the issues of interest for the population with impaired vision.

The contemporary objectives of the present development satisfy all specific needs for equal development of blind, thus the establishment of virtual information center and the systems for the needs of blind will be a step forward for equal participation of blind in social development.

How, When and Where the Information System for Blind Will Be Developed

Thousands of registered magazines (from daily to annual) circulate in our country. How can we provide the blind with their constitutionally guaranteed right on information and with freedom of public word?

There is neither need of details about the theory of communication nor analyze the code channel, code noise and so on. The people with vision will face the dilemma of how to deal with abundance of information because no matter the information is valuable, required and consumable, we are not able physically and biologically to accept and remember it. This abundance will give a wrong impression of the events and will influence undesirably on the actions we undertake.

Contrary to this, the number of blind, who are lonely, constantly increases, even when they are with friends or close family. Therefore, when the postman rings, it is a real holyday for them. It is not because the postman is their real company or one they long for (although he might be

da bi de gotoven za ~a{ ka razgovor) tuku za da mu zablagodarat { to im gi nosi te{ ki - te kni gi i spi sani ja na Brajovo pi smo i li vo zvu~na tehni ka nameneti za ni v. Vedna{ gi otvoraat obvi vki te na zvu~ni te spi sani ja i re~isi, ni koga{ ne mo` e da popu{ tat pred i sku{ eni eto za vedna{ da gi otvorat Brajovi te spi sani ja i kni gi, ta da ja pro~itaat sodr`inata i po nekoj pri log.

Namest o zaklu-ok

Osobeno se ~uvstvuva potrebatata za sistemot na inf ormi rawe na slepi te i odnosi - te vo taa oblast kone~no da se regul i raat i da se uredat vrz osnovi te { to obezbedu vaat traen razvoj na ova a specijal na dej - nost, kako aktiven op{ testven f aktor vo procesot na natamo{ nata af irmaci ja i ostvaruvawe na op{ testvenoto bi tie na Sojuzot na slepi te, vo koj sekoj slep ~ovek }e bi de blagodaren za objekti vnata, navre - mena, cel osna i razbi rli va inf ormaci ja.

Inf ormi raweto na slepi te ne e edinstve - na zada~a na spi sani jata. Ni vnata f unkci - ja e i vo podi gnuvaweto na kul turnoto i obrazovnoto ni vo na slepi te lica i ni v - noto osposobuvawe za sekojdnevna rabota vo organi zaci i te.

Samo neka i maat { to pove}e inf ormaci i vo Brajova, zvu~nata i li vo elektronskata f orma, op{ ti ili specijal izi rani spi sa - nija, ta i da ne moraat, a i ne mo` at od ni v se da is~i taat. Vo edno se soglasuvaat: br - gu im mi nuva vremeto, a ne{ to i nau~u - vaat.

ready for conversation with them), but to thank him for delivering them heavy books and maga - zines in Braille letters or in sound technique. They are eager to open, read and listen to the delivered post immediately.

Instead of Conclusion

There is a specific need for information system for blind. The relations in that field have to be regulated finally on the basis that provide per - manent development of this specific activity, as an active social factor in the process of further affirmation and social existence of the Associa - tion of blind where every blind person will ap - preciate the objectiveness, prompt and complete and understandable information.

The information of blind is not the only purpose of the magazines. Their function is also to de - velop the cultural and education level of blind and their training for everyday work in the working environment.

Let them have as much information in Braille, sound or electronic form, general or specialized magazines, even they cannot or need not read them out. They agree in one thing – that enables time pass quickly for them and at least they learn something.